

D10.2 – Report on results of evaluation and development of ocean/atmosphere parameterisations and coupling schemes

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Lead Partner	AWI
Contributors	Thomas Jung (AWI), Rohit Ghosh (AWI), Malcolm Roberts (MO), Samantha Smith (MO), Alison Stirling (MO), Sally Lavender (MO), Michael Whitall (MO), Oriol Tintó (BSC), Sergi Palomas (BSC), Xavier Yepes-Arbós (BSC)
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Prepared by	Reviewed by	Approved by
Thomas Jung (AWI), Rohit Ghosh (AWI), Malcolm Roberts (MO), Samantha Smith (MO), Alison Stirling (MO), Sally Lavender (MO), Michael Whitall (MO), Oriol Tintó (BSC), Sergi Palomas (BSC), Xavier Yepes-Arbós (BSC)	WP10	EERIE Coordination Team (ECT)

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			Malcolm Roberts (MO)

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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the evaluation and development of ocean–atmosphere parameterisations and coupling schemes within the EERIE project. Our work focuses on advancing physical representations and technical strategies that enable Earth system models to operate robustly at eddy-rich resolution. Four themes were central:

1. **Scale-aware convection** – Development of the CoMorph Trailblazer scheme has demonstrated the feasibility of adapting convection parameterisations to transition smoothly from parameterised to explicitly resolved convection. Idealised tests and global case studies show improved performance compared to previous schemes, particularly in precipitation characteristics and dynamical coupling.
2. **Ocean current feedbacks** – A synthesis of the literature shows compelling evidence that including surface currents in bulk flux formulations is essential for realistic air–sea coupling. Their neglect results in systematic biases in wind stress, energy input, and coupled variability. While no additional sensitivity studies were needed, best-practice formulations have been identified for implementation in EERIE configurations.
3. **Resolution mismatch** – A review of recent coordinated experiments demonstrates that atmosphere–ocean resolution balance is critical for faithfully representing mesoscale processes. EERIE configurations with ~9 km atmosphere coupled to ~5–15 km ocean meshes are well positioned to capture mesoscale interactions, reducing long-standing biases seen in coarser CMIP-class models.
4. **Coupling strategies and costs** – New metrics were developed to quantify the performance overhead of sequential coupling strategies such as IFS–NEMO. For 1 simulated year per day at 4–8 km resolution, sequential coupling was found to incur a 16% computational overhead compared to optimal concurrent strategies, highlighting opportunities for efficiency gains.
5. **Coupling frequency** – Prior studies show that hourly or sub-daily coupling enhances intra-daily air–sea flux variability, reduces SST biases, and improves the simulation of ENSO and extremes. EERIE simulations adopt hourly coupling at kilometre scale, in line with best practice. Additional 30-minute experiments suggest increased sensitivity in eddy-rich regions and regional impacts on fluxes and SST, but without a uniform reduction of biases, highlighting the need for longer and multimodel investigations.

Taken together, these results strengthen the scientific and technical underpinnings of EERIE’s high-resolution coupled modelling framework and provide a foundation for the next generation of atmosphere-ocean interaction studies.

1. Introduction

The fidelity of coupled atmosphere–ocean simulations depends critically on how subgrid processes are parameterised and how fluxes are exchanged across the air–sea interface. With Earth system modelling moving into the kilometre-scale regime, long-standing parameterisations and coupling strategies must be revisited to ensure they remain fit for purpose.

This deliverable documents the progress made in Work Package 10 of EERIE toward this goal. Specifically, it:

- Describes the adaptation of the CoMorph convection scheme for scale-aware behaviour, enabling a more seamless transition between parameterised and resolved convection.
- Reviews the role of ocean currents in surface flux formulations, building on an expanding body of literature that underscores their central role in regulating coupled energetics and variability.
- Evaluates the implications of resolution mismatch between atmosphere and ocean components, with particular reference to the nearly commensurate 9 km EERIE configurations.
- Introduces a new metric to quantify sequential coupling costs in IFS-NEMO and demonstrates its utility in assessing performance impacts at high resolution.
- Explore the impact of coupling frequency on the representation of meso-scale features and large-scale patterns.

By combining targeted model development with systematic evaluation and literature synthesis, this report provides both scientific insight and practical guidance for the design of coupled modelling systems. The results will directly inform ongoing efforts within EERIE, future CMIP7 contributions, and broader community initiatives such as HighResMIP2.

2. Adapting the CoMorph convection scheme for scale-aware, km-scale modelling

a. Summary

EERIE funding has been used to support the development of a scale-aware convection scheme called the CoMorph Trailblazer that operates at km scales. This section:

- Summarises the changes implemented to make CoMorph more scale aware.
- Provides evidence of its scale-aware properties, showing that it is now better at turning itself down and passing over to explicit convection than previous schemes.
- Shows promising initial global NWP performance in a suite of 5km global case studies

The new CoMorph Trailblazer was submitted to the WCRP Hackathon, where it has shown promise relative to other schemes. A publication on the Trailblazer is in preparation.

b. Introduction

Climate and low-resolution NWP models have historically been unable to adequately resolve convective motions in the atmosphere, and have therefore relied on the use of sub-grid convection parameterisation schemes to represent the effects of unresolved convection on the mean flow and the development of convective precipitation. The Met Office is currently developing a new convection parameterisation scheme, CoMorph, to improve the representation of sub-grid convective processes in both climate and weather forecasting models. The initial implementation, CoMorph-A, gave improved coupling to dynamics and radiative properties when compared against the current (6A) scheme (Lock et al, 2024). Since then, the physics changes of CoMorph-A (which include modifications to the boundary layer and cloud schemes) have been ported to the latest atmosphere configuration, GAL9, and the new package is referred to as CoMA9.

This CoMA9 configuration has been used in the Met Office's CMIP6-style simulations contributing to EERIE (using atmosphere resolutions of up to 20km), due to the improvements noted above, as well as indications of reductions in long-standing biases in extreme events such as tropical

cyclones. There is ongoing work to document these improvements as a future deliverable and reference paper.

Following this success, we have adapted the scheme for use at kilometre-scale resolutions, a key step as modelling systems transition toward resolving convective processes more explicitly. As a proof-of-concept, we have focused on modifying CoMA9 to exhibit scale-aware behaviour through the development of a prototype known as the CoMorph Trailblazer (TB).

The performance of the CoMorph Trailblazer has been evaluated in a range of modelling contexts, including idealised simulations based on the TWP-ICE field campaign, and a series of real-world case studies verified against observations. The results of these evaluations will be described in this report, along with a brief outline of future development plans.

This work will also inform future plans for coupled 10km resolution Met Office simulations including for CMIP7 HighResMIP.

c. Idealized simulations of TWP-ICE

To inform and test the CoMorph Trailblazer's scale-aware capabilities, we have conducted a set of idealised simulations which were forced using profiles observed during the TWP-ICE (Tropical Warm Pool International Cloud Experiment) field campaign around Darwin, Australia, during which monsoon conditions were observed (Fridland et al, 2010). These simulations were run on a 200km x 200km domain for 16 days, initialised from midnight on 18 January 2006. Simulations using CoMA9 and the CoMorph Trailblazer were run at horizontal resolutions ranging from 10km down to 1km, to cover the convective grey zone where convection is partly (but not completely) resolved. A 100m resolution reference simulation was also performed using the Met Office regional science configuration for km scales, RAL3.1, in which the convection scheme is switched off, and convective dynamics is explicitly represented.

3. Why is CoMorph a suitable candidate for a scale-aware convection scheme

One of CoMorph's defining features is its smooth-timestep behaviour, which supports improved interaction with model dynamics. We can illustrate this by examining how the sub-grid mass flux relates to the resolved vertical velocity on a given timestep. Let us call the average vertical velocity within a convective updraft, w_{up} , and the fractional area covered by updrafts, s . The mass flux, m , is given by $m = \rho s w_{up}$, where ρ is the density. If we call the vertical velocity outside of the updrafts, w_{env} , then the average vertical velocity in a grid box can be written $w_{av} = s w_{up} + (1-s) w_{env}$. Typically, w_{env} is a lot smaller than w_{up} , and we get a good correlation between w_{av} and $s w_{up}$.

We start by looking at the reference 100m simulation of TWP-ICE described in the above section. Figure 1a shows the relationship between w_{av} and $s w_{up}$ from this simulation. Here the data has been coarse-grained onto 5 km grid-boxes, with w_{up} defined as the mean vertical velocity within a conditionally sampled partition with w greater than zero, and liquid water mixing ratio greater than very small critical values. s represents the fraction of points lying in this conditional sample. There is a very high correlation between w_{av} and $s w_{up}$, as might be expected in a highly skewed vertical velocity field such as this.

Next, we derive the equivalent quantities for simulations that use a convection scheme to represent the updrafts. This time $s w_{up}$ comes from the parametrised convective mass flux, m , so that $s w_{up} = m/r$ (noting for completeness, in our case, we also need appropriate adjustment of the units and also divide by g to ensure w_{up} is in m/s rather than Pa/s).

This time, any link between w_{av} and w_{up} depends on an additional step from the dynamics. When the sub-grid convection scheme is active in a particular grid-box, the air within that grid-box is warmed due to the imposed environmental subsidence from the mass flux scheme. The resulting horizontal temperature (and therefore buoyancy) excess relative to adjacent columns results in resolved ascent to adjust the atmosphere back to a weak horizontal temperature gradient. If the convection scheme acts smoothly, the dynamics has time to build up a response that matches the convective heating, and a similar correlation to the reference scheme emerges.

Figure 1b shows how the mass flux and resolved vertical velocity relate to each other in the control 6A scheme. This is much less correlated than the reference simulation suggests should be the case. We attribute this to the intermittent nature of the convection scheme, making it hard for the dynamical response to convective heating to respond in an appropriate way. For example, the resolved response might take a few timesteps to adapt to the convective heating, but by which time the scheme might have turned itself off.

Finally, we look at a recent version of CoMorph (Figure 1c). This shows a high degree of correlation between the resolved vertical velocity and the mass-flux derived $s w_{up}$, showing similar behaviour to the reference simulation. Here the smooth-timestep behaviour of the scheme allows the dynamics to build up a consistent response to the convection scheme.

This enables CoMorph to be very much better coupled to the dynamics, which is an important property if explicit and sub-grid convection are to coexist within a model-simulation.

Figure 1: Relationship between convective updrafts and the resolved scale. w_{up} is plotted against resolved w_{av} for 5km grid-boxes using coarse-grained 100m resolution data (left), the 6A scheme (centre) and CoMorph (right). Each colour corresponds to a different time within the TWP-ICE simulation (see section 5 for more details).

3.1. Modifications to CoMorph for Trailblazer

Summary of the changes

The CoMorph Trailblazer (TB) was created by introducing targeted modifications to *CoMorph-A*, designed to induce scale-awareness. The changes implemented on top of CoMA9 are:

1. A reduction of the initial moisture perturbations which control the water supply to the convection scheme.
2. Reduction of the initiating mass-flux from each height to turn down the impact of the convection scheme.
3. Increased rain evaporation at high rain rates
4. Increased entrainment rates through modification of the ‘Radius Ramp’ relationship between updraft radius and rainfall. (See section 4.1 below.)

Modifications of entrainment rates via the precipitation ‘Radius ramp’

In CoMorph-A, entrainment, e , into the updraft is set to be an inverse function of the thermal radius: $e = 0.2/R$, where R is set to be proportional to a length scale set by the boundary layer turbulence, as follows:

$$R = A L.$$

$$L = K_m/s_w$$

is the ratio of the turbulent viscosity K_m to the standard deviation of vertical velocity, s_w as predicted by the turbulence scheme. L typically correlates with the boundary layer depth. In the absence of precipitation, A is set to 0.45. In the presence of precipitation, however, the radius is allowed to increase further as a function of grid-mean precipitation according to:

$$A = B (1 + C \min(p, p_{max})/(p_{max})), \text{ with } B = 0.45, \text{ and } C = (2/0.45 - 1)$$

When $p = p_{max}$ or greater, $A = 2$, and so $R = 2 L$. (See Lock et al 2021)

This function enables larger-radius plumes to be initiated in the presence of precipitation, giving a highly simplified representation of the generation of cold pools through evaporative cooling in precipitating downdrafts, and their subsequent enabling of larger-radius plumes to be initiated at gust front edges.

The dependence of CoMorph's thermal radius on grid-mean precipitation, however, leads to a resolution sensitivity once the grid size becomes small enough to contain only a small number of precipitating downdrafts – where the convection scheme needs to be active, the grid-mean precipitation is now more intense.

For the CoMorph-A Trailblazer, which is to be operated at km scales, we therefore need to modify this functional form to take into account the grid size, and its relationship to grid-mean precipitation within the grid box.

The link between grid-mean precipitation and grid-size will clearly depend on the organisation present in the domain, and therefore, likely the synoptic conditions generating the precipitation. What we aim to achieve here is a plausible increase in the precipitation threshold needed in the grid-box in order to attain the lowest entrainment rates, and in such a way as to retain consistency with the original CoMorph-A formulation when run with a grid-box of 50 km.

To calculate an approximate resolution dependence, we have used simulations of the TWP-ICE case study at 100m, and domain size 200 km, and investigated how the precipitation field varies as a function of scale. For a series of instantaneous rainfall fields taken at sub-daily (in this case every 20 hours, but there is little sensitivity to this) intervals through the simulation, the domain is divided into 50km boxes. Within each box, we identify the location of peak precipitation, and draw a circle of radius G around that peak. We then plot the mean precipitation within radius G , against the mean precipitation in the parent 50km grid box for all the 50km sub-boxes in the domain (in this case there are 16 sub-boxes). This yields a scatter plot as seen in figure 2.

Figure 2: Showing the mean precipitation in a ring of diameter 25km centred on the maximum precipitation in the grid box, compared with the mean precipitation of the parent 50km box. Each point represents one of the 50km boxes that the domain has been subdivided into. The best fit slope is shown as a red dashed line, and the black dotted line shows the 1:1 line for reference.

Figure 2 shows that the rain surrounding the peak in the 50 km grid box is more intense than the average for the whole grid box. (Noting that the circular area will not sit exactly within the 'parent grid box' because the circle's centre is determined by the location of the rainfall maximum.) We take the best fit slope and then plot that ratio as a function of diameter, 2G. This is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Showing how the rainfall within a given diameter divided by the rainfall within a grid box of 50km varies as a function of diameter. Each rainfall ratio point is the best fit straight line found from the whole domain and averaged over all times. The green envelope shows the range of values over the different times. The grey dashed line shows the best fit assuming a linear function in log space. Left is a linear plot; right is a log-log plot. The red dashed line uses a slope of -1, as is used in the Trailblazer.

The functional form approximating this simulated rainfall is given by:

$$p_{max}(dx) = p_{max_ref} dx_ref / \text{Max}(dx,dy)$$

Where $dx_ref = 50 \text{ km}$, and $p_{max} = p_{max_ref} = 3.5e-4 \text{ kg m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. The fit is shown in figure 4.

This functional form allows the entrainment to vary as a function of grid-size, giving some preliminary scale-awareness to the scheme, allowing it to be run at different resolutions. A significantly improved, and more physically justifiable cold-pool representation is being prepared for CoMorph-B.

3.2. Scale-aware performance in idealized simulations of TWP-ICE

Figure 4 shows a time-series of surface precipitation, averaged over the entire domain for the TWP-ICE period. The temporal development of the mean precipitation is very similar at all resolutions from 10km down to 100m, owing to the strongly forced nature of the simulation. This

allows us to compare the behaviour of different-resolution simulations for the same time of output, and therefore to probe a range of different convective regimes covered by the case.

Figure 4: Time series of horizontally-averaged surface precipitation at the various resolutions (colours). Resolutions from 10km to 1km used the Trailblazer scheme. Analysis times are marked by vertical dashed lines.

For initial analysis of the 100m simulation fields, the four different times marked as vertical lines in Figure 5 were chosen: the surface precipitation at each of these times is shown in Figure 5. Time 3 is during the period of maximum rainfall on day 6, and the convection is highly organised on larger scales. Time 4 is in the second half of the simulation when there was relatively little large-scale organisation. Times 1 and 2 have intermediate amounts of organisation.

To estimate the fraction of the total convective activity that should be sub-grid (i.e. produced by the convection scheme) for a simulation with grid-spacing Δ , the vertical velocity (w) data from the 100m resolution simulation was smoothed using a Gaussian filter to remove scales smaller than Δ . This gives an approximation to the resolved field at this resolution. This “resolved” field is then removed from the original field to give an approximation to the “sub-grid” field. Then comparison of the mean mass flux within all cloudy updrafts in both the original and sub-grid field gives an approximation to the fraction of the mass flux that should be sub-grid. This analysis was performed at a height of 2 km, which is above the convective cloud base but below any ice cloud. This was repeated for a range of smoothing scales, representing different theoretical resolutions, resulting in the curves for different times, shown in Figure 6. Although the curves are similar in

shape, for the different times, they differ in scale, for example most of the convection becomes sub-grid at a much smaller grid-spacing for time 4 (black line), when the convection was mainly disorganised, meanwhile the large-scale organised convection at time 3 still has a significant resolved component at relatively large grid-spacings.

Figure 5: Surface precipitation rates ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) at the four chosen times (using different colour scales): time 1 (top left), time 2 (bottom left), time 3 (top right) and time 4 (bottom right).

Figure 6: Fraction of mass flux that should be sub-grid across a range of grid spacings. Colours refer to the four different analysis times.

CoMorph passes any precipitation that is generated to the microphysics scheme, which then represents its fall to the surface. There is therefore no natural distinction between large-scale and convective rainfall (as there is with the 6A scheme), and so an additional diagnostic has been added which estimates the surface precipitation that has come from the convection scheme. From this we can calculate the fraction of total surface precipitation that is produced by CoMorph rather than by the combination of resolved convective motions and the microphysics scheme. Figure 7 shows the time-series of this sub-grid precipitation fraction for the different resolution CoMorph simulations. The symbols show the fraction of convective mass flux that should be sub-grid according to the 100m simulation analysis. The Trailblazer (right panel) behaves in a more scale aware manner than CoMA9 (left panel), for example, the Trailblazer produces a lower fraction of the total rain in the 1km simulations than CoMA9. Figure 8 shows the same comparison, but in a different form – this time we look at the fraction of sub-grid precipitation as a function of scale, for the four different times marked in Figure 5. This figure shows that the Trailblazer more readily gives way to explicit convection at finer scales than the original CoMA9. The discrepancy between the

100m curve and the CoMorph points at time 3 could be linked to a problem of normalisation when convective structures span the domain as in this case. This will be refined in future iterations.

Figure 7: Time-series of sub-grid convective precipitation fractions at various resolutions. We would expect the sub-grid fraction to reduce for higher resolution simulations. Symbols show what the 100m mass flux analysis suggests this fraction should be. Left panel shows CoMA9 without scale-aware adaptations, right panel shows the CoMorph Trailblazer.

Figure 8: Showing the fraction of mass flux that is expected to be sub-grid as a function of scale (black); with blue circles showing the actual sub-grid fraction for CoMorph, and orange stars the equivalent for the new Trailblazer runs.

3.3. Global atmosphere-only tests at N2560

Initial global tests have used an atmosphere-only configuration for straightforward comparison with other configurations. This has been run across a selection of NWP 2020/21 case-study dates, allowing verification with observations using the Met Office TRUI (Trial Results User Interface). CoMA9_TBv1p2 is referred to as CoMA9_TB in some cases but these all correspond to the same configuration. Data from the Integrated Multi-satellitE Retrievals for GPM (IMERG) v7 are used for comparison and accessed from <https://gpm.nasa.gov/data/directory>.

The spatial distribution of precipitation is broadly similar across all model configurations (Figure 9), with similar differences from the observational (IMERG) data. All model configurations show light precipitation over northern Europe and Russia which may not be captured by the satellite data. Although all datasets are regridded to the same grid, GAL9 (Fig 9 e&f) gives a smoother distribution than the CoMA9 configurations (Fig 9 b-d) and observations (Fig 9a). N2560 CoMA9_TB (Fig 9c) better captures the intensity of precipitation off the coast of northwest Australia but may produce too much precipitation over the Indian Ocean.

Figure 9: Accumulated precipitation over 5 days (start date of 20200101T0000Z) from (a) GPM-IMERG v7, (b) CoMorph control, CoMA9 at N1280 resolution, (c) N2560 CoMorph Trailblazer, CoMA9_TBv1p2, (d) N1280 CoMorph Trailblazer CoMA9_TBv1p2, (e) N2560 GAL9 (previous 6A scheme) and (f) N1280 GAL9. All have been regridded to the same (IMERG) grid.

Figure 10: Fraction of precipitation that is produced by the convection scheme for different model configurations and resolutions (a) N1280 with CoMA9 (no changes), (b) N2560 CoMorph Trailblazer, CoMA9_TBv1p2, (c) N1280 CoMorph Trailblazer, CoMA9_TBv1p2, (d) N2560 GAL9 and (e) N1280 GAL9

We now look at how the fractional contribution of convective precipitation changes in the global model runs. Figure 10 shows the fractional contribution of the convective precipitation rate to the total precipitation for: the CoMorph control run at N1280 (Fig 10a); the CoMorph Trailblazer (CoMA9_TBv1p2) at N2560 (Fig 10b) and N1280 (Fig 10c); and the previous 6A convection scheme (GAL9) at N2560 (Fig 10d) and N1280 (Fig 10e). At N1280, the trailblazer shows a reduction in convective fraction relative to the control version of CoMorph, CoMA9 (Fig 10 a,b), and this reduces further with higher resolution (Fig 10b, c) to 60-70% across most of the tropics at N2560, while still producing similar total precipitation (Fig 9), as desired. GAL9 is more insensitive to the resolution changes, with more than 90% of the rain coming from the convective partition over most of the tropics (Fig 10 d,e)

Figure 11 shows pdfs of tropical rainfall, representing the fractional contribution of each precipitation rate to the total precipitation over the tropics (20S – 20N). Precipitation rates are

calculated for every 3-hour accumulation over all grid points in the tropics and separated into 100 bins based on Klingaman et al. (2017). The previous version of GPM-IMERG (v6; dotted black line) overestimated the intense precipitation rates relative to v7 (solid black). The distribution from the CoMorph Trailblazer at N2560 (CoMA9_TBv1p2, solid green) compares well with the latest IMERG product. The original CoMorph (CoMA9) configuration at N1280 preferentially rained at a particular rate due to the precipitation ramp. Moving to the Trailblazer version (CoMA9_TBv1) at N1280 reduces this and pushes to higher precipitation rates but keeps much of the behaviour of CoMA9. Increasing resolution makes little difference to the distribution of precipitation rates in GAL9 (red lines).

Figure 11: Histogram showing the fractional contribution to total precipitation over the tropics (20S – 20N). Calculated from 3-hourly accumulations. GPM 30-min rates are converted to 3-hourly for comparison. Both GPM versions 7 and 6 plotted for precipitation rate.

The use of a set of NWP case-study dates allows verification of the model with both analyses and observations. To check the mean-state, it is important to look at the biases in variables such as temperature and winds as the run progresses, which generally increase throughout the model simulation. The biases in tropical temperature (left) and winds (right) at the end of the 5 days are

shown in Figure 12 plotted against both analyses (upper) and observations (lower). The changes from CoMA9 to CoMA9_TBv1p2 have reduced the tropical temperature biases below 250 hPa, giving it a similar magnitude to GAL9. Interestingly changing resolution does not have much impact on these biases. There is a slight warm bias relative to both observations and analyses at around 150 hPa but it still lies within a reasonable range. The wind-profile biases are shown to increase in the upper troposphere in the Trailblazer (CoMA9_TBv1.2), although the analyses have a slow bias so the error is slightly reduced when comparing against observations. This behaviour will be examined in more detail as part of wider Met Office evaluation of the CoMorph Trailblazer.

Figure 12: Mean error at T+120 averaged across the full set of 2020/21 case-study dates (24 startdates) in (a) tropical temperature profile and (b) tropical wind speeds relative to analyses. (c) and (d) as (a) and (b) but relative to observations.

3.4. Conclusions and Future Work

In this report, we have shown that CoMorph has good coupling to the dynamics, and this makes it a good candidate for a scale-aware scheme. We have shown that relatively simple modifications give CoMorph an improved ability to turn itself down as the convective size increases relative to the grid scale, and that this ability can be seen both in the idealised TWP-ICE case study, and in global NWP case studies.

The Trailblazer has been shown to perform competitively in NWP case studies, producing realistic precipitation patterns and improved histograms of rainfall, and the results shown here are shortly to be submitted for publication. A significant effort at the Met Office is now underway to evaluate the scheme further in global 5km coupled NWP runs.

While CoMA9 remains a robust option, its **diurnal cycle** performance at climate resolutions remains a concern. To address this, we are developing *CoMorph-B*, a new variant with improved representation of cold pool outflows. However, CoMorph-B is not yet scale-aware. Once the base scheme is finalised, we aim to introduce scale-aware features, leading to a future *CoMorph-C* version. In *CoMorph-C*, additional dependencies on grid-scale properties, such as the initiating mass flux and relative humidity initial perturbations, will be introduced.

Ultimately, scale-aware schemes such as the Trailblazer and future CoMorph variants enable atmospheric models to benefit more fully from increased resolution, including the improved representation of orographic effects and dynamical structures across all scales.

4. Impact of including ocean currents in the coupling

Accurate computation of air–sea fluxes of momentum, heat, and moisture hinges critically on accounting for the relative motion between atmosphere and ocean. Surface currents modify the effective wind stress and turbulent heat fluxes, particularly over energetic mesoscale features. Neglecting currents in bulk formulae leads to systematic overestimation of wind stress and heat fluxes, biases in ocean mixing and circulation, and distorted coupled variability (e.g., ENSO, storm tracks) (Chelton et al., 2004, 2007; Dawe and Thompson, 2006; Jullien et al., 2020; Pacanowski, 1987; Renault et al., 2016, 2017, 2019; Zhang et al., 2013).

Subsequent research utilizing increasingly realistic eddy-rich coupled models has further substantiated this conclusion. For example, Wilder et al. (2023) derive a geostrophic eddy energy dissipation rate resulting from the interaction between the large-scale wind field and mesoscale ocean currents. This interaction is articulated through the concept of relative wind stress, defined as the difference between wind speed and current speed. They emphasize that accurately parameterizing this relative wind stress is crucial for precise estimation of energy dissipation in oceanic eddies. This study highlights that the inclusion of ocean currents in stress calculations reduces gross wind power input into the ocean by 20–35% (Duhaut and Straub, 2006), with a damping of eddy kinetic energy by 10–30% (Zhai and Greatbatch, 2007). In twin simulations with eddy-resolving models of the North Pacific, Wu et al. (2024) found that incorporating mesoscale ocean–atmosphere (MOA) coupling results in approximately 25% more subtropical mode water, driven by enhanced latent heat release and displaced storm tracks. Furthermore, another study employs high-resolution coupled simulations over the Gulf Stream to demonstrate that current

feedback significantly alters surface stress curl patterns and boundary layer circulations, particularly during winter, thereby modulating both weather-scale and seasonal climate impacts (May and Bourassa, 2023). Similarly, a recent study has shown in global high-resolution models that current feedback (CFB) dampens eddy activity by approximately 30%, stabilizes western boundary currents, modulates sea surface temperature (SST) gradients and heat fluxes, and influences extratropical storm-track intensity by up to approximately 15% (Renault et al., 2024).

These post-2023 studies—spanning dissipation theory, water-mass formation, coupled stress dynamics, and storm-track modulation—consistently demonstrate that neglecting ocean currents introduces substantial biases in flux computations and destroys fidelity in coupled dynamics.

In light of the robust and converging evidence across both pre-2023 foundational work and more recent studies, the literature provides a *clear and comprehensive picture* of the critical role of surface currents in air–sea coupling. Including relative winds in flux calculations—not only reduces systematic overestimation of fluxes but directly affects eddy energetics, water-mass formation, storm-track behavior, and overall coupled model realism.

Therefore, no additional sensitivity experiments were performed in this project, as the existing literature is sufficiently unambiguous. To avoid raising questions about why such experiments were not conducted earlier, the focus remains on implementing the well-established formulation and highlighting our alignment with best practices demonstrated by contemporary high-resolution modeling studies.

5. Impact of resolution mismatches between atmosphere and ocean

The way atmosphere and ocean components are coupled in Earth system models depends on their relative resolution. When the two meshes differ strongly, the exchange of heat, momentum, and freshwater across the air–sea interface can become distorted. A large body of work has shown that resolution mismatch may lead to undersampling of ocean variability, oversmoothing of important gradients, and even spurious sources and sinks of energy when land–sea masks or remapping procedures are not fully consistent (Craig et al., 2017; Streffing, 2023). For instance, when atmospheric cells cover large areas while the underlying ocean model resolves eddies and sharp sea-surface temperature fronts, the small-scale ocean signal often fails to project onto the atmosphere. This weakens the variability of surface fluxes and reduces the strength of coupled feedbacks that are otherwise known to be important for storm tracks, tropical convection, or air–sea exchanges in boundary current regions (Chelton and Xie, 2010; Renault et al., 2016). Conservative remapping procedures, which are designed to ensure flux conservation, help to avoid

gross imbalances but tend to dilute sharp gradients, especially in regions like the Gulf Stream or the Southern Ocean, thereby muting their imprint on the atmosphere (Hewitt et al., 2020).

The importance of matching atmosphere and ocean resolution has been highlighted in several coordinated high-resolution experiments. Results from HighResMIP and other eddy-resolving coupled studies indicate that simulations in which the atmosphere and ocean have comparable resolution show clear improvements. These include a more realistic position and strength of western boundary currents, a reduction of the longstanding bias in the tropical Pacific cold tongue, and a more faithful representation of storm track variability and blocking (Roberts et al., 2019; Schiemann et al., 2017; Vannire et al., 2020). Mesoscale air–sea interactions, such as the wind–eddy and wind–front feedbacks, also emerge more naturally in such balanced configurations (Small et al., 2019).

Against this background, the configurations employed in EERIE occupy an interesting position. In the most ambitious setup, both the atmosphere and the ocean are run at a resolution of around nine kilometres (ICON and IFS.NEMO). This nearly commensurate choice should allow a very close representation of mesoscale coupling processes and reduce the dependence on corrective remapping strategies. In such a setting, we expect many of the shortcomings associated with resolution mismatch to be absent, with the atmosphere being able to respond directly to the eddy-rich ocean fields and vice versa. The alternative configuration (IFS-FESOM), which couples a nine-kilometre atmosphere to an ocean mesh varying between five and fifteen kilometres, introduces a modest degree of mismatch. In regions where the ocean resolution is closer to five kilometres the coupling will still be highly consistent, but in coarser parts of the mesh, where grid spacing approaches fifteen kilometres, some of the small-scale ocean variability may be underrepresented in the fluxes seen by the atmosphere. The resulting atmosphere–ocean feedbacks are likely to be somewhat weaker than in the commensurate case, yet the mismatch remains far smaller than in traditional CMIP6-class models, where a fifty- or hundred-kilometre atmosphere is typically coupled to an ocean of one-degree resolution.

Literature also points to strategies that can mitigate the remaining issues. Remapping schemes designed to be energetically consistent help to reduce artificial imbalances (Craig et al., 2017), while stochastic coupling methods can re-inject variability that would otherwise be lost through oversmoothing (Rackow & Juricke, 2020; Streffing, 2023). More generally, there is increasing interest in scale-aware parameterisations that adjust the representation of subgrid processes to the relative resolutions of the coupled components (Zanna and Bolton, 2020). Taken together, these developments suggest that the EERIE configurations, particularly the 9–9 km setup, are well positioned to advance our understanding of coupled atmosphere–ocean processes at the mesoscale. The slightly mismatched 9–5/15 km setup is expected to perform very well too, though with some attenuation of small-scale feedbacks in coarser ocean regions.

6. Sequential Coupling Cost in IFS-NEMO

The ECMWF employs NEMO as the ocean component within its coupled atmosphere–ocean model. Unlike initiatives such as EC-Earth, ECMWF adopts a sequential coupling strategy, where the ocean model is integrated as a function call inside the IFS executable. A limitation arises from the existing definition of the *coupling cost metric* found in the literature: by construction, it evaluates to zero for sequentially coupled models, despite the fact that sequential coupling is known to introduce a measurable performance impact. To address this gap, we at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) are developing a new metric that can quantify sequential coupling costs, with results currently being prepared for publication.

In this document, we illustrate how this proposed metric can be applied to assess the sequential coupling cost of the IFS–NEMO system. Our analysis focuses on the IFS–NEMO coupled model configured with the TCo2559 grid (~4 km resolution) for the atmosphere and the eORCA12 grid (~8 km resolution) for the ocean. All experiments were conducted on the MareNostrum 5 supercomputer. Although this particular configuration is not used within the EERIE project, the same sequentially coupled IFS–NEMO system is employed there. This means that the methodology and the proposed metric are directly applicable and can provide valuable insights into the performance evaluation of EERIE model configurations as well.

Component-level timings were inferred from IFS–NEMO run outputs. In this configuration, the computational cost is dominated by the atmosphere, which accounts for ~80% of the total runtime. By conducting a series of runs with varying resource allocations, we constructed an analytical performance model for both components, enabling us to predict their execution speed as a function of node count. Figure 13 demonstrates that the chosen performance model reproduces the observed scalability with high accuracy.

Figure 13. Scalability curves of IFS and NEMO. Crosses show measured performance, while solid lines represent model fits to the data. Performance is expressed in simulated days per day (SDPD) as a function of node count.

We then used the analytical models to evaluate the sequential coupling cost at a target speed of 1 Simulated Year Per Day (SYPD). The same models also allow us to estimate the theoretical concurrent performance, which represents the optimal resource usage if both components could run simultaneously.

Figure 14. Scalability of IFS, NEMO, and coupled configurations (sequential vs. concurrent). The concurrent line corresponds to the theoretical best concurrent configuration computed from the analytical models. The horizontal line marks 1 SYPD. Vertical lines indicate the required resources for each configuration. The shaded area represents the sequential coupling cost.

From the analytical models (Figure 14), we obtain:

$$N_{seq}(1_{SYPD}) = 458.8_{nodes} , N_{NEMO}(1_{SYPD}) = 46.1_{nodes} , N_{IFS}(1_{SYPD}) = 338_{nodes}$$

This implies that, under sequential coupling, achieving 1 SYPD requires 74.4 additional nodes compared to the optimal concurrent setup. We therefore find that the sequential coupling cost is:

$$\text{Sequential Coupling Cost}(1_{SYPD})=16\%$$

The origin of this overhead is straightforward: in the sequential setup, NEMO is forced to run on 458.8 nodes, far more than the ~46 nodes sufficient for its workload. This leads to inefficient scaling of the ocean component due to its relatively small computational load and increased communication overhead. By contrast, in an ideal concurrent coupling setup, the ocean can be assigned a modest, efficient allocation while the atmosphere scales independently to meet the target throughput. In this way, our definition of the Sequential Coupling Cost makes explicit the

performance penalty of sequential strategies, providing a clear and quantitative measure of their impact on scalability and resource efficiency.

7. Impact of coupling frequency

Previous studies have demonstrated that the frequency of coupling in global climate models significantly influences the simulation of various processes. Specifically, hourly or sub-daily coupling enhances the variability of air–sea fluxes. For instance, hourly coupling has been observed to increase momentum flux variance by up to 50%, freshwater flux variance by 100%, and net heat flux by a factor of 15 compared to daily coupling (Tian et al., 2017). Furthermore, it has been reported that disregarding intra-daily sea surface temperature variability reduces the amplitude of the El Niño–Southern Oscillation by approximately 15% and weakens teleconnections (Masson et al., 2012; Terray et al., 2012).

High-resolution modeling studies further demonstrate that frequent coupling mitigates sea surface temperature biases, enhances overturning circulation (Hewitt et al., 2016), and improves the representation of extreme weather events, such as tropical cyclones and heavy precipitation (Scoccimarro et al., 2017). Hewitt et al. (2016) assert that only the integration of high ocean and atmospheric resolution with hourly coupling significantly reduces sea surface temperature biases and bolsters overturning circulation. Sub-hourly coupling in cloud process schemes, as elucidated by Santos et al. (2021), results in substantial alterations in cloud forcing and precipitation characteristics. In conclusion, the studies indicate that increased coupling frequency more effectively resolves intra-daily feedback and enhances the simulation of large-scale climate modes and extreme events, particularly when combined with high spatial resolution.

In the EERIE project, kilometer-scale coupled Phase 1 simulations, including the IFS-FESOM model at 9 km atmospheric and minimum 5 km oceanic resolutions, are coupled at hourly intervals. As corroborated by numerous prior studies, we have achieved a high-frequency coupling standard between the atmosphere and ocean in our EERIE simulations, thereby reaping the intended benefits of such coupling frequency. Nevertheless, questions persist regarding the potential outcomes of employing even higher sub-hourly coupling frequencies and whether such changes might alter the model's behavior. To investigate this hypothesis, we conducted an additional set of experiments, commencing from the year 2005 of the main historical simulation, and subsequently diverging by altering only the coupling frequency from 1 hour to 30 minutes between the atmosphere and ocean. This experiment was conducted over a total of 8 years, followed by preliminary diagnostics to assess the potential effects of these changes in coupling frequency.

Figure 15. The standard deviation of daily sea surface height (SSH) in the experiment with 30min coupling frequency (Left) and the difference of the same from the experiment with 1 hour coupling frequency for the same period of time (Right). Units are in meters.

Figure 15 illustrates the standard deviation of daily sea surface height (SSH) in the experiment conducted with a 30-minute coupling frequency. This figure highlights the primary oceanic regions rich in eddies on Earth and provides a qualitative representation of areas where high eddy kinetic energy is anticipated. The right panel presents the difference in SSH between the experiments with 1-hour and 30-minute coupling frequencies. A discernible response to changes in coupling frequency is evident, particularly over the main eddy-rich regions, such as the Kuroshio, Agulhas, and North Atlantic Currents. Additionally, anomalies are observed globally; however, these are of lower magnitude and may constitute noise, given the analysis period of only eight years. Nevertheless, the pronounced signal of higher magnitude anomalies over the eddy-rich regions suggests an intensified level of air-sea interaction, potentially altering the variance in daily SSH at higher sub-hourly coupling frequencies.

We further examine alterations in the mean state of key parameters between these two experiments under varying coupling frequencies (Fig 16). The modifications in the mean geopotential height at 500 hPa indicate increased pressure over the Arctic and decreased pressure anomalies over the Antarctic (Fig 16, top left). Additionally, the height fields exhibit a dipole pattern above the North Atlantic current, where significant changes in eddy activity are observed, along with similar variations in sea surface temperature (SST) and associated turbulent heat fluxes (sensible and latent). Among the turbulent heat fluxes, the latent heat flux contribution predominates in these regions. Beyond the eddy-rich areas, a positive SST anomaly is observed over the Barents Sea region, which corresponds with a positive turbulent heat flux in that area. This suggests that a higher coupling frequency would result in cooling in this region. The cause of such cooling warrants investigation, as it may provide insights into the cooling issue encountered over the Arctic in IFS-FESOM simulations. Given the similarity in the pattern of changes in turbulent heat fluxes and SST over the eddy-rich regions, it can be inferred that these changes are attributable to variations in coupling frequency. Based on the SST bias observed in historical simulations, some of these changes could potentially reduce biases around the Kuroshio regions

or the subpolar North Atlantic. However, it also appears that there are regions, particularly at high latitudes, where such changes could exacerbate biases if other factors are not addressed. Therefore, overall improvement in bias is contingent upon multiple factors and is not solely dependent on further increases in coupling frequency.

Figure 16. Between the 1-hourly and 30-minute coupling frequency experiments, the difference in the 8 year annual mean climatology of 500 hPa geopotential height (Z500, top left) in meters, sea surface temperature (SST, bottom left) in Kelvin, sensible heat flux (SHF, top right) and latent heat flux (LHF, bottom right) in Watts/m².

In summary, we conducted an eight-year simulation with sub-hourly coupling frequency and demonstrated that such changes in coupling frequency primarily affect ocean eddy activity, particularly in eddy-rich regions. The simulation also reveals discernible signals in the changes in mean sea surface temperature (SST) and turbulent heat fluxes, with an imprint on the large-scale circulations above the main eddy-rich region. However, to enhance confidence in these results, a longer simulation would be necessary. To gain a clearer understanding of how these changes alter eddy characteristics, further investigation will examine eddy composites to decipher their effects on the statistics of cyclonic and anticyclonic eddies in the simulations. We do not observe an overall improvement in bias due to the higher coupling frequency; rather, some regional improvements are noted. To achieve a broader understanding of the potential effects of increasing the coupling frequency, a multimodel analysis would be beneficial.

8. Summary and conclusions

This report highlights the importance of advancing parameterisations and coupling strategies in step with the resolution frontier. Key findings include:

- CoMorph Trailblazer successfully introduces scale awareness to convection parameterisation, enabling improved precipitation representation and smoother interaction with dynamics. This approach sets the stage for future developments (CoMorph-B, CoMorph-C) that incorporate cold-pool dynamics and further resolution dependence.
- Ocean current inclusion in surface flux formulations is no longer optional: a wealth of recent studies demonstrate its decisive role in modulating wind stress, eddy energetics, storm tracks, and water-mass formation.
- Resolution balance between atmosphere and ocean models is critical. EERIE's ~9 km setups substantially reduce biases compared to traditional CMIP6-class models and allow coupled mesoscale feedbacks to emerge naturally.
- Coupling strategies matter for performance. The newly defined sequential coupling cost metric provides a transparent way to quantify inefficiencies, which amount to ~16% at target throughput, motivating consideration of concurrent alternatives for future systems.
- Previous work suggests that hourly coupling strengthens air–sea interactions and improves large-scale variability and extremes. EERIE's kilometre-scale setup follows this approach. Preliminary sub-hourly (30 min) experiments indicate regional sensitivities, particularly in eddy-rich regions, but no consistent global bias reduction, pointing to the need for extended analyses.

Together, these advances demonstrate that careful attention to parameterisation, resolution, and coupling methodology can significantly enhance both the realism and efficiency of high-resolution Earth system models. EERIE's developments thus represent an important step toward establishing the robust, scalable modelling framework required for CMIP7, Destination Earth, and digital twin initiatives.

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